

DECIPHER

Holistic decision-making for climate & environment

Deliverable 2.2: Strengths and limitations of economic methods and tools as procedural policy instruments

Legitimizing, rational, or enlightening? Economic modelling, policy innovation, and the adoption of the 55% emission reduction target in the European Union

LEGAL DISCLAIMER

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Scope of the document	<p>While much has been written about the need for economic modelling and ex-ante impact assessment – for example, in the form of cost-benefit analysis, cost effectiveness analysis, or multi-criteria evaluation – relatively little is known about the effect of these techniques on policy choices and, thereby, outcomes. In this task, we conceptualize the use of economic methods as a procedural policy tool (Bali et al., 2021) that alters the dynamics of the policy process and policy design. Specifically, we examine the characteristics that influence the use of economic methods and tools for environmental policymaking, investigate their influence on eventual policy design, and assess how they alter effectiveness and legitimacy of the policy. The data on the use of economic methods will be collected through focus groups discussions and semi-structured interviews with selected stakeholders identified in WP1. This task furthers an understanding of the strengths and</p>

limitations of the methods and tools used in impact assessment to increase their use in practice by contributing to the advancement of economic tools in WP4 and the development of the decision framework in WP5. Early findings will inform the stakeholder engagement process of WP1.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Whether low-carbon policy innovations would lead to adverse economic, environmental, and social impacts has been a major concern associated with climate change mitigation. While such impacts can be assessed using economic models, past assessments have been criticized for their narrow focus on economic impacts. To make the assessments more holistic, recent endeavours in modelling aim at including other aspects—such as biodiversity—into a new framework of economic policy appraisal. At the same time, the use of these advances in policymaking processes must be ensured. Yet, how economic modelling outputs are utilized in these processes and when they enable policy innovations is not well understood.

In this study, we address this gap by conducting an empirical analysis of the role of macroeconomic modelling in the adoption of the 55% greenhouse gases emissions reduction target for 2030 by the European Union (EU). This is an innovative policy that represented a significant increase in ambition and laid the foundation for the adoption of numerous other policies in the subsequent Fit-for-55 package. The framework for analysis we synthesized is based on the literature on knowledge utilization in the academic discipline of policy sciences. This framework recognizes that knowledge can influence policymaking in three primary ways: (i) as a source of ‘rational’ learning about effective policies; (ii) as a ‘legitimizing’ source for prior policy beliefs or preferences; and (iii) as an ‘enlightening’ source that informs conceptual understanding of the actors involved. The methods involved content analysis of 28 key documents and 12 semi-structured interviews with economic modellers and policymakers involved closely in the policy process.

Our findings indicate that while the outputs of three macroeconomic models informed different elements of policy they were used by different actors in different ways. First, they were utilized by the European Commission to legitimize a previously articulated preference for the 55% emission reduction target as a policy objective. Second, the Parliament used them in an enlightening way to motivate higher targets. Third, they were used rationally for the choice of policy instruments in the following policy cycle of the “Fit-for-55” package. Our analysis shows that economic modelling further influenced the dynamics among different actors in the policy process.

Based on these findings, we reflect on the strengths and limitations of economic modelling as a tool that influences the policymaking process. In our case study, a key strength of economic models was their ability to provide knowledge that informs different aspects of policymaking. Another strength of economic models was their capacity to depoliticise issues in the policy debate. Further, economic models helped foster policy innovation and set an ambitious target for emissions reduction. However, as a limitation, economic modelling did not cover the interests and views of some key stakeholders of the policy. An implication of this analysis for economic modelling is

that the incorporation of scenarios, indicators, and levels of analysis of interest to diverse actors can facilitate a more informed policy debate.

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1 Introduction

The world is in pressing need to accelerate the energy transition through new policies, but concerns about their economic impacts often pose a major barrier to their adoption (Leipprand & Flachsland, 2018). There are several approaches to evaluate such economic impacts (Horschig & Thrän, 2017), yet past assessments of economic impacts often rely on narrow economic indicators that do not capture the full picture. To make the assessments more holistic, recent endeavours in economic modelling aim to include other aspects, such as biodiversity¹, into a new framework of economic policy appraisal. Policy processes increasingly anticipate economic impacts of policies on GDP, employment, or competitiveness, for example, through ex-ante impact assessment studies (Herbst et al., 2012; Ittersum & Sterk, 2015). However, a recent review on the use of evidence in policymaking revealed that knowledge is most frequently used for symbolic or tactical purposes, instead of a direct translation of the results into policy design (Ouimet et al., 2024). Still, the reviewed studies do not investigate modelling specifically, so it remains unclear whether and how the results of economic modelling are utilized in policymaking.

Studies that have focused on the use of economic models in policymaking have compared the interactions between policy analysts working with economic models and policymakers in different contexts (Butter & Morgan, 1998a). They find that influence on policymaking depends on the way that institutional structures are used rather than the type of structures (Butter & Morgan, 1998b). For the use of economic models in the context of energy modelling, Royston et al. (2023) investigated how politics shape the development of models for policymaking. However, they do not report on how models influence policy design specifically. This in turn is specified by Süsser et al. (2021), who studied the different ways in which economic energy models affects policymaking along the policy process. Despite the contribution of these studies for the understanding of how economic models are used in policymaking, they do not differentiate between the variety of ways in which modelling results can inform the policy process.

In this study, we conceive modelling outputs as a form of knowledge that can be used in policy processes. Several academic studies have addressed the role(s) of knowledge in policymaking (Sedlačko & Staroňová, 2015; Spruijt et al., 2014). For example, research on knowledge utilization (Weiss, 1979) has shown that there are different functions that knowledge fulfils in policymaking. First, it fulfils an instrumental function when knowledge is used directly to solve policy problems. Second, political use of knowledge to legitimize preconceived positions has also been observed, and even found on a regular basis (Ouimet et al., 2024). Third, knowledge can catalyse

¹ See e.g. <https://decipher-horizon.eu/>

'enlightenment', i.e. conceptual understanding about policy problems or solutions, when it indirectly contributes to evidence on a particular policy issue.

There has been some research into what determines the presence of different types of knowledge utilization. For example, it depends on the structure and degree of conflict within and between expert coalitions (Funke et al., 2021; Weible, 2008). External influences of knowledge use practices from other countries can also lead to changes in knowledge use (Marchevska, 2024). Most studies find that political use prevails, while other forms of use are found to coexist, even at the same time (Ouimet et al., 2024; Rissi & Sager, 2013). The use of knowledge can channel policy conflicts, but misrepresented expectations about the role of knowledge in policy processes may cause conflict (Dorren & Wolf, 2023). However, none of these contributions on the role of knowledge in policymaking have particularly addressed economic energy modelling. Furthermore, it is not clear how economic modelling contributes to the creation of policy innovations in the energy transition (Goyal et al., 2022; Huber et al. forthcoming). Lastly, these studies do not differentiate how knowledge in general and modelling in particular influence the dynamics among different actors in the policy process.

Even in the wider literature on climate modelling, studies have not examined the different uses of modelling in policymaking, despite numerous other insights on model-policy interactions. Some models get utilized repeatedly for policymaking, creating a lock-in dynamic (van Beek et al., 2020). Models can function as eye-openers, as arguments in dissent, as vehicles in creating consensus, and as tools for management of a system (van Daalen et al., 2002). Modelling itself is a process with different steps that can each influence policymaking in different ways, and at different stages (Calder et al., 2018). In the development of a model, several decisions are involved that can impact its influence on policymaking. When preparing a model study, modellers and policymakers (co-)define problems, objectives, modelling approach, assumptions, and input data (Midttun & Baumgartner, 1986; Royston et al., 2023; Süsser et al., 2021). These decisions cannot always be made objectively and depend on values and the belief system of the agents involved (Silvast et al., 2020; Vecchione & Chalabi, 2021). A few of these decisions are highly influential on modelling outcomes and represent uncertainties of the model (Pye et al., 2018). However, none of the above studies utilize theoretical frameworks on the use of knowledge in policymaking.

The literature on impact assessment has also looked into how assessments have been used in policymaking (Adelle et al., 2012; Dorren, 2021; Dunlop, 2016), but has not clarified the role of modelling therein (Süsser et al., 2021). The role of assessments can be discerned into the formal role it is assigned in the procedural guidelines, and a practice role of its actual use. While the formal role is often intended to be a rational one, its instrumental use is found to be limited. Instead legitimizing, strategic and symbolic use of it are prevailing (Hertin et al., 2009).

In this study, we address these gaps by formulating the question: *What was the role of macroeconomic modelling in the policy process of setting the EU 2030 climate targets? We focus our empirical analysis on the adoption of the 55% emission reduction target for 2030 of the European Union (EU), a major policy innovation that paved the way for the subsequent “Fit for 55” package. We particularly focus on macroeconomic modelling, as results from this type of analysis are especially instructive for climate mitigation policy. In Section 2, we will present insights from the literature on knowledge utilization regarding learning, legitimizing, and enlightening use of knowledge, and synthesize existing literature on the use of modelling in policymaking into these categories. Section 3 will introduce our case study research design and methodology consisting of a qualitative content analysis of policy documents and semi-structured interviews. In Section 4 we present the results of our analysis in a reconstruction of the decision-making process of the 55% target and the role that macro-economic modelling outputs played therein. Finally, section 5 concludes with our contribution to literature on knowledge utilization, and a reflection of the strengths and limitations of modelling in influencing policy design, effectiveness and legitimacy, from which we derive implications for policy analysts and economic modellers.*

2 Analytical Framework

There are only a few studies that scrutinize how economic energy modelling in particular is used in policymaking (Royston et al., 2023; Süsser et al., 2021). To derive theoretical insights about the use of modelling in policymaking, modelling results can be conceptualized as a type of knowledge that underlies different uses in policymaking (e.g. Weiss, 1979). Thus, in this section we will first give a general overview of the literature on knowledge utilization, including rational, legitimizing, and enlightening forms of knowledge uses. For each of these, insights from existing analyses on the use of economic modelling are presented. Since there are only a few we will mainly rely on Süsser et al. (2021) and Royston et al. (2023). This section does not reflect our own observations or perspectives but represents a review of the insights that existing literature on knowledge utilization and the use of modelling in policymaking has generated.

The results of economic modelling can be conceptualized as a type of knowledge that interacts with policy processes. The subject of knowledge has been examined in many research areas in public policy, with different research foci and methodological underpinnings (Sedlačko & Staroňová, 2015). For this study, we consider the literature on knowledge utilization to be especially informative, as it has investigated how knowledge is used in policymaking. Following the seminal work of Carol Weiss (1979), many scholars have studied what role knowledge takes in policymaking and

differentiated rational, legitimizing, and enlightenment functions. When knowledge is used to solve problems of policymaking, it fulfils a rational function for policymaking. When knowledge is used to advance positions of actors involved in a policy process, it fulfils a political use. There are also instances where scientific insights serve as a “source for ideas, information, or orientations to the world” (Weiss, 1977), thus enlightening policymakers or representing a conceptual use of knowledge.

2.1 Rational use

Often it is assumed that knowledge is directly used to inform and solve policy problems. This instrumental use rests on a rational ideal approach to problem solving, where research is conducted to solve a policy problem and the decision then follows the research findings (Weiss, 1979). This creates the expectation that a specific study generates immediate impact on choices and detects problems of knowledge utilization as problems of research communication, or practice-orientation. However, this requires willingness to engage with surprising findings that stand in conflict with ones’ own beliefs. In practice, this does not occur often, as policy entrepreneurs, attempt to link policy solutions and problems with political opportunities (Weible, 2008).

If applied instrumentally, modelling outputs can shed light on the consequences of decisions (Calder et al., 2018). Models influence policy at different stages in the modelling process. Energy models for example help assess the impacts of reaching different targets (Süsser et al., 2021). The models’ impact depends on experience policymakers have with energy models, and general climate policy ambitions of the government, as well as the level of conflict in the policy process (Süsser et al., 2021).

2.2 Legitimizing use

Knowledge can also be used politically to legitimize preconceived policy ideas (Boswell, 2009; Weible, 2008). Policymakers often base their decisions on the constellation of interests around policy issues, or ideology, and select information that aligns with these (Weiss, 1979). Moreover, the organizational structures of policymaking can lead to a selective processing of information, as organizations compete over authority over a policy issue (Daviter, 2015). Administrations and policymakers therefore suppress conflicting knowledge claims to create stable perceptions of policy solutions, to expand policy authority and exercise control (Boswell, 2009; Daviter, 2015; Weible, 2008). However, shifts of authority within administrations can create episodic and delayed shifts in knowledge use, and can therefore catalyse major policy change (Baumgartner & Jones, 1993; Daviter, 2015). Whether or not change occurs when authority changes depends on the structure of such organizations, for example the degree of administrative specialization, the rigidity of departmental boundaries, and the overlap of responsibilities across policy organizations are characteristics that may influence the degree of political use of

knowledge (Daviter, 2015). If these are set up in certain ways they create political competition and facilitate engagement with disconfirming data (Daviter, 2015, p. 499). Next to this legitimization of political positions, Boswell (2009) also differentiates a legitimizing function. Organizations use knowledge for the perception of their own legitimacy, to demonstrate that their decisions are well found. Additionally, knowledge can also aid in symbolizing a political response to a problem, while actual policy measures are lacking (Hertin et al., 2009).

2.3 Enlightenment use

Often expertise creates enlightenment among policy actors, as they expand their conceptual knowledge scope (Weiss, 1979). It is also often referred to as conceptual use (Ouimet et al., 2024; Weible, 2008), leading to a more indirect change from knowledge input. Over a longer period, the accumulation of knowledge can change perceptions of policymakers on what policy problems and solutions are. In the beginning, there is usually a reluctance to accept contradictory information that shifts radically to attempts of overcompensation of past decisions (Weible, 2008).

Models can contribute to an enlightening use of knowledge by exploring futures and facilitating a shared understanding of the world, when modellers construct the model (Calder et al., 2018). For energy policy, economic models in particular have been found to help explore policy options (Süsser et al., 2021).

In the present study we will look at which of these uses of modelling outputs occurred in the process of setting policy targets. Further, we will investigate how the modelling analysis was set up to inform policymaking, and in what ways economic modelling contributed to policy innovations. The next section describes how we executed research on these issues.

3 Methods

There is not much empirical research about how economic models have been utilized in policy processes. To generate insights into this, we adopted a case study research approach (Yin, 2018). The aim of such a case study is less to produce insights that are representative and can be generalized to larger population. Instead, the aim is to create an extensive examination of a typical single case of policymaking to illustrate how macroeconomic modelling has been involved. Based on these empirical findings, we engage in a theoretical analysis in comparison to the literature on the use of economic models and knowledge utilization.

3.1 Case selection and background

We selected the 55% greenhouse gas emissions reduction target of the European Union for 2030 as a revelatory case for the use of economic modelling for innovative policymaking, because it is the most recent fully adopted climate target at the EU level. It has been adopted on June 30th, 2021, and replaced the previous target of 40% greenhouse gas emission reductions that was set in 2014, as a continuation of the 20% emission reduction target for 2020 that was set in 2008. The EU Commission is known for its extensive technical expertise and utilization of modelling capacities. Furthermore, the EU's 2030 Climate Target represents an innovative policy that laid the foundation for the adoption of numerous other policies in the subsequent "Fit-for-55" package, with which the European Union displays its aspirations to be a political leader for global climate action.

In this analysis, we will focus on the policy process of selecting the current 55% target for the EU's 2030 Climate Target that took place from 2019–2021. It is important to note that this is only a part of the whole "Fit-for-55" package, which included many other policies, with their own impact assessments, and many other types of economic models. It also excludes impact assessments for previous 2030 targets that modelled the impact of lower emission reduction targets. Within the impact assessment "Stepping up Europe's 2030 climate ambition. Investing in a climate-neutral future for the benefit of our people", which is our specific focus in this study (European Commission 2020b), several economic energy models are involved.

Roughly, the economic models that were involved in the impact assessment can be distinguished into: (i) techno-economic models that simulate the consequences of the introduction of a policy on the energy market and are used to simulate the feasibility of technological changes in the energy system; and (ii) macroeconomic models simulate the corresponding economic impacts on society, for example on economic growth, competitiveness, and employment (Nakata, 2004). While techno-economic models were often cited by environmentally-concerned actors to illustrate the feasibility of a renewable energy system, macroeconomic models were often cited by industry-related actors to highlight economic risks of such an energy system (Herbst et al., 2012). It is therefore interesting to focus on macroeconomic modelling. There is a vibrant academic debate on how to develop macroeconomic models that better inform energy policymaking (Bauer et al., 2023).

The impact assessment included three macroeconomic models: An application of JRC-GEM-E3 by the Joint Research Centre at the European Commission, E3ME by Cambridge Econometrics and E-QUEST by DG ECFIN. These represent different theoretical assumptions. JRC-GEM-E3 is a computable general equilibrium (CGE) model that is based on neo-classical economics (Matsumoto & Fujimori, 2019), which were for a long time dominant in assessing economic impacts (Hafner et al., 2020). More recently, ecological macroeconomic models, such as E3ME have been developed that represent post-Keynesian economics (Hafner et al., 2020; Rezai et al.,

2013). E-QUEST is a dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) that is built on New-Keynesian assumptions and contains a two-region, multisector model specifically developed for climate and energy related policy analysis. (European Commission 2020b).

The policymaking process of the EU's 2030 Climate Target evolved in the following procedure (Figure 1). First, the European Commission developed a proposal for a new policy. In this case, the European Climate Targets for 2030 were part of the proposal for the European Climate Law in March 2020 (European Commission 2020a). An impact assessment for the Climate Target 2030 was conducted and published on September 17th, 2020 (European Commission 2020b), along with the amended proposal (European Commission 2020d).

Figure 1. Schematic policy process of the 55% target

Subsequently, the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union develop their positions. In the Parliament, a rapporteur is appointed to draft the Parliamentary Report. It is then discussed in and adopted by the responsible Committee (European Parliament 2020a), before entering the parliamentary readings, where it may be adopted (or not) (European Parliament 2020b). Almost simultaneously, the Council of the European Union develops and adopts the Council's General Approach (Council of the European Union 2020). The Council of the European Union consists of representatives of the respective national ministries, and is also called the Council, or the Council of Ministers. It must not be confused with the European Council, which consists of the head of states or head of governments. Although the European Council is not formally involved in the legislative procedure of the European Union, it can adopt general political directions for the European Union, called Council Conclusions. Then, the Council and the Parliament enter negotiations,

with the Commission mediating between the two in the Trilogues. Finally, the European Climate Law was adopted on June 30th, 2021, as part of the “Fit for 55” package and the European Green Deal. The results are structured following this policy process and differentiates the use of economic modelling between the Commission, the Parliament and the Council.

3.2 Data Collection

We use 29 documents and 12 semi-structured interviews to generate evidence about the use of economic modelling. At first, in September 2024, we gathered policy documents from the websites of each European organisation, for example legislative acts, impact assessment reports, stakeholder consultation reports, and policy proposals pertaining to the Climate Law or the 2030 Climate Targets. We complemented these documents with targeted searches for news articles from the websites of Politico and Euractive (ANNEX 1 List of policy documents and other sources) to create an overview about the policy process, modelling results, and policy outcome of the Climate Targets.

Once the overview was established, we conducted a total of 12 semi-structured interviews between September and October 2024. We held seven interviews with economic modellers of each of the afore mentioned organizations, which were involved in the creation of the impact assessment. We also interviewed five policymakers/policy analysts working with economic models from the Parliament, the Council of the European Union and the Commission that were involved in the policy formulation and decision-making of the EU’s 2030 Climate Targets. The interviews focused on the decision-making process on the 55% target, and the impact and role of modelling on the final policy design. The interviews followed an interview guide (ANNEX 2: Interview guide), but interviews were open for other questions and follow-up questions to keep a natural flow of the conversation and to retain openness about events that were important from the interviewees’ perspective. The interviews lasted 45-75 minutes each, were held online as a Microsoft Teams meeting, and were thereafter recorded and transcribed.

3.3 Data Analysis

Based on the collected documents and interview transcripts, we conducted a qualitative content analysis. We established a coding scheme that is based on the interview guideline and thus represents the theoretical issues that we want to inform with our analysis. With this scheme, we coded the responses of the participants regarding the modelling process, the policy process, and the role of modelling (ANNEX 3: Coding scheme). The coding was conducted utilizing the software Atlas.ti 9.0.18 for Windows (Scientific Software Development GmbH, 2023). Once all the text sequences had been coded, we investigated the individual snippets in each coding category and synthesized their content into a narration of the events in this case (section 4

Results). Interview sources are referenced with MOD for economic modellers and PM for policymakers. We specifically focused on the main analytical question:

1. How has macroeconomic modelling been utilized for policy design?

Following from our codes, this analysis identifies the different uses of knowledge building on a separation of the different steps in the policy process, and the different actors participating within it. Based on the description of this evidence and the case, we then generalized theoretical relationships that we compared with the existing theories of knowledge utilization (section 5.1 Insights into knowledge utilization literature). We then reflected on the implication of our findings for how economic modelling might impact on policy legitimacy and policy effectiveness (section 5.2 Policy legitimacy and effectiveness). For this reflection, we also reverted to responses from interviewees about the effects of economic modelling on policy legitimacy and effectiveness. In section 5.3 Strengths and limitations of economic models as procedural policy tools then, we reflected on the strengths and weaknesses of economic models with regards to their role as a procedural policy instrument. This represents a contrast, yet also an addition to other work in the DECIPHER project, where the main question is their capacity to model specific issues. Finally, we conclude with practical implications for policy analysts and economic modellers that derive from our findings of the case study (section 5.4 Implications for policy analysts and economic modellers).

As with every case study, some limitations of this methodology must be borne in mind. While it represents a robust examination of a case of EU policymaking, patterns of utilization of models might differ in other contexts, such as national/ regional levels, authoritarian regimes, or non-western states. Further, interviews have been conducted at least 3 years after the adoption of the policy, and thus might contain memory loss and lack of detail. The availability of interviewees further restricts what can be documented about the process. A large deal of the negotiations, especially in the Council, the European Council and in the Trilogues are not public and interviewees are hard to access and to open up about negotiations that happened behind closed doors. Despite these limitations, our case study is an important and scarce illustration of how economic models are being utilized in policy processes. It provides more depth into the analysis of how economic modelling has been utilized than other studies we know of and the information that we gathered remains valid, even though it might miss out some of the details of the non-public negotiations.

4 Results

We identified several functions of knowledge utilization depending on different aspects of the macroeconomic modelling analysis. However, first we briefly introduce the scope of the macroeconomic analysis in the impact assessment. Thereafter, we dive into nuances of how exactly economic modelling outputs were used in the process.

The macroeconomic analysis in the impact assessment for the European Union's Climate Targets 2030 served to assess the macroeconomic impacts of a 50% and a 55% reduction of greenhouse gas emissions compared with 1990 levels (European Commission 2020b). The economic impact was assessed by modelling effects of the climate targets on GDP, competitiveness, employment and investment. Impacts on these were calculated differentiating two scenarios of behaviour of the rest of the world. In the first scenario, there is global climate action, and all countries strive towards achieving the 1.5°C target of the Paris Agreement. In the second scenario, there is fragmented action, where the rest of the world only implements their current Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Furthermore, the effect of different policy mixes ranging from regulatory to pricing mechanisms was explored. Three different models were applied to calculate impacts: The models are the JRC-GEM-E3 model from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, the E3ME model from Cambridge Econometrics, and the E-QUEST model from the Directorate-General for Economic and Financial Affairs (DG ECFIN).

4.1 Legitimizing use for the 55% target

The economic modelling analysis in the impact assessment of the European Climate Targets for 2030 had a legitimizing function for the previously articulated preference of the 55% target. While the modelling exercise was conducted in an open-ended manner, and the modelling results were not manipulated, distorted, or presented in a selective way (MOD 2; MOD 3; MOD 4), the modelling exercise was designed to assess a 50%, and a 55% target only (European Commission 2020b). The Commission deemed these targets politically feasible for EU Member States in the Council of the European Union (PM 3). This allowed for a swift adoption of the target, which functioned as a rationale for motivating the policy changes that would follow in the "Fit for 55" package (PM 3). It is helpful to take a closer look at the circumstances of this choice for understanding how this particular use came about in detail.

One of the most crucial prerequisites for achieving the legitimization of the 55% targets was reducing the scope of the impact assessment to an assessment of a 50% and a 55% target. The choice of excluding the assessment of higher or lower targets is motivated in the impact assessment. On one hand, targets lower than 50% would not fulfil the political mandate of the presidency, because they do not represent a

sufficient increase of climate ambition compared to the existing policy mix (European Commission 2020b). Indeed, the Commission had previously calculated that the existing climate policies would already reach a 45% emission reduction by 2030, which would already overshoot the previous 40% reduction target of the EU for 2030 (European Commission 2018). On the other hand, targets higher than 55% were excluded, as they would front-load efforts strongly and increase challenges of a faster transition, while a 55% target was already seen in line with responsible global emission pathways. (European Commission 2020b). However, while this seems to represent a rational choice, the choice of these targets has not been based on previous economic analysis (PM 5). Instead, it can be traced back to the political guidelines of the President of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen:

“We have to be more ambitious when it comes to our 2030 targets. I want to reduce emissions by at least 50% by 2030. However, to achieve real impact the world has to move together. The EU will lead international negotiations to increase the level of ambition of other major emitters by 2021. By this date, I commit myself to putting forward a comprehensive plan to increase the European Union’s target for 2030 towards 55% in a responsible way. This plan will be based on social, economic and environmental impact assessments that ensure a level playing field and stimulate innovation, competitiveness and jobs” (von der Leyen 2019, p.6).

The choice of anchoring those targets in her program is likely the result of her effort to become President of the European Commission after the European Elections 2019 (PM 3). Normally, the position for the president of the European Commission would be given to the “Spitzenkandidat” of the largest party after the elections. There was however not enough political support among Member States for the European People’s Party’s (EPP) candidate Manfred Weber (Crum, 2023). Therefore Ursula von der Leyen (EPP) was introduced, but she needed to secure support from the Parliament, especially from the Socialist and Democrats (SD) and the Greens-European Free Alliance (Greens/EFA) (PM 3). Since the European Elections were strongly framed around climate change mitigation, she included a preference for a 55% target in her political guidelines (von der Leyen 2019; PM 3), knowing that the European Parliament had previously adopted a 55% reduction target for its resolution on the 2018 UN Climate Change Conference in Katowice, Poland (COP 24) (European Parliament 2018).

This political choice of the 50% and the 55% target framed the development of the subsequent policy formulation. Both goals were later included in the Green Deal Communication (European Commission 2019), as well as the proposal for a European Climate Law, and finally the impact assessment of the new 2030 climate target (European Commission 2020a). The result of the economic modelling analysis in the impact assessment was that both targets would have a limited impact on GDP (European Commission 2020b) and therefore the Commission recommended the adoption of a 55% target (European Commission 2020c).

The recommendation of the Commission for a 55% target was a strong argument in the upcoming negotiations within and between the Council of the European Union and the European Parliament. In the Council, a majority of Member States backed a 55% target (Simon 2020a; Oroschakoff and Mathiesen 2020a), but coal-reliant and poorer member states linked a decision on the target to discussions on the EU budget and specifically the Just Transition Fund (Oroschakoff 2020b). They also wanted the decision to be made by Heads of State in the European Council instead of environmental ministers in the Council (Oroschakoff 2020b). Therefore, it was finally placed on the agenda of the European Council, where remaining issues should be solved by heads of states or governments (PM 3). These negotiations were also utilized by Poland and Hungary for bargaining advantages related to ongoing issues with their compliance to the rule of law (Oroschakoff and Mathiesen 2020b). After lengthy discussions and a failure to reach agreement at the European Council meeting in October 2020 (European Council 2020a; Cienski 2020; Oroschakoff and Mathiesen 2020a), the Head of States finally adopted the 55% target in their Council conclusions in December 2020 (European Council 2020b; Mathiesen and Oroschakoff 2020b; Simon 2020b). This unanimous decision marks a decisive point in the adoption of a 55% target, because it represents a complex compromise at the highest political level (Council of the European Union 2020; Taylor 2021; PM 3).

During this process, in the Council, insights from economic models were first discussed in the preparatory bodies (PM 3). These discussions were supported by the evidence of the low economic impact of a 55% target from the impact assessment of the Commission (PM 3), which, however, did not allow for insights into impacts at national level, which lie at the core of the Member States interest (PM 5). It is unclear to what extent national analyses of the macroeconomic impact informed the positions of the Member States, but most Member States would have capacities to conduct their own national modelling exercises (PM 3, PM 5). Therefore, insights from the economic modelling of the impact assessment generally legitimized the choice of a 55% target in the Council, but did not cover national economic impacts, which is central for the discussions in the Council.

Interviewees emphasized that the “impact assessment was not just to rubber stamp the proposal that had been issued in the guidelines, but it was a proper impact assessment” (PM 5). Economic modellers who were involved also stressed that there was no manipulation of the analysis or suppression of certain results (MOD 2, MOD 3, MOD 4). This indicates that there was a degree of openness in case modelling results would have counterargued the feasibility of the climate targets, and thus a even a somewhat instrumental use for the assessment of the Climate Target.

4.2 Enlightening use for higher targets

In the Parliament, the economic analysis of the Commission functioned more like an enlightenment that high climate ambition does not necessarily come with adverse

economic impacts (PM 4). The Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI) appointed Jytte Guteland as a rapporteur for the European Climate Law that included the Climate Target for 2030. In her report, she pledged for a 65% target, which was amended in the ENVI committee to a 60% target (European Parliament 2020b) and became adopted by the Parliament on October 8th, 2020 (European Parliament 2020a; Oroschakoff 2020; PM3; PM4). Despite requests from Parliament that the Commission should also assess a 60% target, the Commission was not willing to spend resources on such an additional assessment, because they were doubtful of its political feasibility (Mathiesen and Oroschakoff 2020a; Simon 2020a; PM 4). This had a negative impact on the Parliament's position, as they could not anticipate impacts of a 60% target on the labour market and the EU as a whole (PM 4). As a result, the 60% target did not possess the same authority as the 55% target of the Commission and could therefore not influence the negotiations in the Trilogues later on (Taylor 2021; PM 4). Finally, the 55% reduction target was adopted on June 30th, 2021, in the European Climate Law (EU 2021/1119).

Additionally, for other parts of the analysis, such as the exploration of policy instruments, the use of economic modelling was more instrumental.

4.3 Rational use for the policy instrument design of the “Fit for 55” package

Another role of the economic analysis was to explore broad design options for policy instruments. For this, four different main scenarios for policy mixes were included in the analysis (PM 5). First, a baseline scenario was created simulating the economic effects of the existing policy mix (PM 5; MOD 4). Second, there was one scenario called REG that simulated a focus on regulation-based instruments to reach the 55% target. A third scenario called CPRICE simulated the extension of carbon pricing instruments to reach the 55% target, with no additional regulatory policies. Lastly, the MIX scenario represents a combination of REG and CPRICE, simultaneously increasing pricing instruments and the other policies, albeit less than in REG (European Commission 2020b). The MIX scenario was found to have the least negative impact on the economic indicators and was chosen as a design principle for the “Fit for 55” package (PM 5).

The result of a mix of regulatory and pricing mechanisms was used in a rational way for the policy instrument design of the subsequent policy process of the “Fit for 55” package. Even before this analysis, it was already clear that the existing foundation of policies, was already set and its further development was not up for debate (PM 5). This includes, for example, the Emission Trading Scheme (2003/87/EC), the Effort Sharing Regulation (EU 2018/842), the Renewable Energy Directive (EU 2018/2001), or the Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU). Nevertheless, what the economic analysis added was an indication for the design of additional instruments (PM 5). For example, in the building sector this indicated a development of regulatory policies, such as the

Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, alongside the introduction of the Emission Trading Scheme for road transport and buildings as a pricing mechanism (PM 5). Once this indication was taken, more detailed assessments of the economic impact were conducted for each policy individually (see e.g. European Commission 2021). Therefore, the economic analysis for the climate targets informed the tendency towards a mix of regulation and price-based tools in a rational way (PM 5).

Furthermore, distributional implications found from the analysis revealed the necessity of compensatory measures like the Social Climate Fund (Weitzel et al., 2023). Part of the economic analysis was a relatively new model extension that has been applied for the first time in the impact assessment for climate targets 2030 (MOD 4). It found that the proposed policy changes may cause a proportionally high burden for low-income households that could be mitigated by compensating them. Part of the economic assessment was then also to find the most effective way of compensating those households, for example through lump sum transfers, or tax recycling (European Commission 2020b). The rationale for the political will of these redistributions, and subsequently developments of this model extension gained more traction with social concerns of climate policies. These were expressed in movements such as the 'Gilets jaunes' (yellow jackets in English), but also followed from climate mainstreaming within the Commission, getting, for example, the Directorate General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL) more involved in climate policy making (MOD 4). As a result, the modelling innovation regarding distributional implications of the new Climate Target for 2030 led to the adoption of the Social Climate Fund, which can be considered a policy innovation (MOD 4). Both examples of the policy instrument scenarios and the distributional modelling extension illustrate rational functions of the utilization of economic modelling.

An overview over all identified uses of economic modelling can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview over identified uses of economic modelling

KNOWLEDGE TYPE	ACTORS	PURPOSE	PROCESS STAGE	KNOWLEDGE	REFERENCES
Legitimizing use	European Commission	Assessing the economic impact of a 50/55% target	Impact assessment	The targets have limited economic impact.	European Commission 2020b, PM 3, PM 5, von der Leyen 2019
Enlightening use	European Parliament	Assessing the economic impact of a climate target	Parliamentary report	Higher targets might also have low economic impact	European Parliament 2020b, European Commission 2020b, PM 4
Rational use	European Commission	Assessing the impact of policy instrument design	Impact Assessment	A mix of regulation and pricing instruments has least impact	European Commission 2020b, PM 5
Enlightening use	European Commission	Assessing the distributional impacts of the climate targets	Impact Assessment	Proportionally high burden on low incomes makes Social Climate Fund necessary	Weitzel et al 2023, MOD 4, European Commission 2020b

5 Conclusion and Discussion

5.1 Insights into knowledge utilization literature

The case study showcases how different uses of modelling outputs can coexist within the same process when looking at the modelling results in more detail and when differentiating various aims of a modelling exercise or impact assessment. This confirms an analysis of the use of economic modelling for the previous 40% Climate Targets of the EU for 2030, which found that modelling was mostly used politically, but also showed signs of being used to ensure learning (Süsser et al., 2021). Our case adds to this with a more in-depth investigation of knowledge uses in the European Union. First, the case showed that macroeconomic modelling served a legitimizing function for the previously articulated policy objective of 55% emission reductions. Second, macroeconomic modelling served the Commission rationally for future choices on the design of the policy instrument mix. Third, utilization of models differed between actors, with the Parliament employing more an enlightening use of the impact assessment instead of a legitimizing use of the Commission. These findings go beyond usual analyses found in the current body of literature on knowledge utilization by including nuances of knowledge use, for example how all kinds of different uses next to each other, depending on the knowledge object in focus (i.e. policy objective vs. policy instruments).

The legitimizing use in this case is mirrored in the selectiveness of the 50% and 55% targets in the design of the impact assessment. Time pressure for policymaking—as was the case for the adoption of the 55% target—can result in less open economic modelling as another factor in Süsser et al.'s (2021) list of factors that influence the use of economic models in public decision-making for policy. In contrast, the impact assessment of the more recent 2040 climate targets were conducted under less time pressure and explored the ideal target more openly (PM 5).

In line with Weiss's (1979) notion of knowledge utilization, the legitimizing use then often reflects the position of what is feasible politically, regarding the position of all stakeholders. A motivation for the legitimizing use can be the generation of authority for individuals in a particular organization, for example when the candidate to the President of the Commission, Ursula von der Leyen, articulated a preference of 55% to gain support in the Parliament.

In the case of several legislative chambers like the EU, the roles that economic modelling plays can be different for different venues and stages in the policy process. In the Council, the macroeconomic analysis on EU level had less importance, as member states were more interested in the impacts on national scale, and it is

unclear to what extent national analyses contributed to the decision. However, they used the assessment quite instrumentally, adopting the 55% target. In the Parliament, the assessment of the Commission was used more as enlightening role that indicates that impact even of higher target on economy would not be high. The lack of impact of their target on the overall decision highlights the authority of an (economic) impact assessment.

5.2 Policy legitimacy and effectiveness

Legitimacy entails the confidence of the public that the government makes justified and appropriate decisions (Dahl, 1998). It involves the acceptance of policies through citizens, and the government's fairness and suitability (Peters, 2019). While in our case knowledge has been used to legitimate policymaking, there is limited evidence if economic modelling increased the perception of legitimacy of the 55% target. It can be argued that it contributes to a more transparent and more evidence-based discussion on the economic impacts of the new climate target. This way, countermeasures against negative impacts could be taken in form of the Social Climate Fund, which probably increased the overall legitimacy of the policy. However, an overly political use of economic modelling can also risk affecting policy legitimacy when the authority of an analysis becomes questioned. In this case, there are no indications that this happened and therefore it can be supposed that economic modelling supported the legitimacy of the EUs 2030 Climate Target.

Effectiveness relates to "whether policy goals have been achieved and whether this can be attributed to the policy" (Huitema et al., 2011). In comparison to the effect of economic modelling on policy legitimacy, it is even harder to assess the definitive impact of economic modelling on policy effectiveness of the 55% target. In the case of the EU, there is little reason to believe that a climate target alone without accompanying policy instruments would achieve such a target, as Member States often do not comply with EU policy. The recognition that derives from economic modelling that pursuing a 55% target will not impact the European economy can however be beneficial for the effectiveness of such a target, as it counterargues concerns towards setting and eventually achieving such a goal. Furthermore, regardless of the result of the modelling analysis, economic modelling can indicate undesirable and indirect effects of the policy, such as the unproportionate high burden on low incomes. Once unmasked, these can then be dealt with to ensure the effectiveness of a policy. All in all, the use of economic models seems to enable more effective policymaking as it allows to acknowledge impact of climate policy innovations and deal with economic concerns that could threaten the success when such policies are implemented.

5.3 Strengths and limitations of economic models as procedural policy tools

Our reflections on the influence of economic modelling on the effectiveness and legitimacy of the 55% target point towards a central strength of economic modelling. It can enhance the effectiveness of the policy and creates policy legitimacy in the right modelling set-up. Additionally, our analysis reveals some key strengths and limitations of economic models as procedural policy tools.

A key strength of economic models is their ability to provide knowledge that informs different aspects of policymaking. On the one hand, they informed the choice of policy goal of the 55% reduction target, and on the other hand the policy instrument mix of the later “Fit for 55” package. From this it can be inferred that economic modelling in contexts beyond this case study might also influence the selection of policy agendas, for example through the inclusion of new system relationships into a model. Further, it raises the question whether economic models might also be suitable to inform the evaluation of policy effectiveness.

Another strength of economic models is their capacity to depoliticise issues in a policy debate. Actors might articulate all sorts of different claims that can result in clashes of different positions and thus conflict about policy issues that impede progress in policy processes. Models can help to resolve those conflicts by providing an analysis that is accepted by actors attending in these policy debates. In the case of the EU 2030 Climate Target, the analysis of the economic impact of the 55% target trumped the argumentation for other targets, both for Member States that were not in favour of such a high target, and the Parliament, or other environmental NGOs that were in favour of higher reduction targets.

Our analysis indicates also the significance of economic modelling for the generation of policy innovations and illustrates the relationship between the two. Firstly, results from economic modelling have contributed to the policy innovation of the 55% target by legitimizing it. Furthermore, economic modelling has further informed the development of the innovative Social Climate Fund. These are two ways of influencing policy innovation through economic modelling, but others are thinkable. For example, through the political learning that is induced by analyses of economic modelling, policy inventions can be equipped with the evidence that is needed for a successful adoption of a policy innovation. Thus, our analysis shows how policy innovation can be catalysed by legitimising policy results, but also by innovations in the modelling itself.

However, this case does not only point to strengths, but also potential issues of the identified way of utilization of economic models. Firstly, economic modelling in this case did not cover the interests and views of the key stakeholders of the policy. For example, Member States had concerns about national impacts of the new climate target, but the results of the economic analysis in the impact assessment did only

show impacts at EU level and not on national level. Further, it is unclear to which extent Member States modelled national impacts themselves. As a result, the selectiveness of the representation of stakeholders' perspectives in the economic modelling might influence policy processes in a way that it could erode legitimacy of the resulting policy. At the same time, economic modelling could be made more inclusive, if it considers other actors than the Commission, for example the Parliament with its suggestion for higher targets and the Council with national analyses. This could function as an addition to modelling innovations for more inclusiveness, such as stakeholder engagement tools. Once the preferences of more stakeholders are represented in the economic analysis, this issue could be turned into a strength, adding to the legitimization of the policy.

Regardless of its impact on legitimacy, access to economic modelling is a powerful resource for actors. They can lend argumentative power to certain actors and result in the inclusion and exclusion of actors in a policy debate. In our case for example, the Commission gained authority over decision-making of the target through the impact assessment. With this piece of authoritative knowledge, it altered policy dynamics by elevating its preference of a 55% target over preferences in Parliament and Council.

5.4 Implications for policy analysts and economic modellers

Our analysis has shown that modelling can simultaneously serve a variety of tasks and uses in the policymaking process, while increasing policy legitimacy. Therefore, economic modelling should be embraced when possible, and also designed to serve several tasks. It might enable enlightening uses even if the analysis did not exactly cover specific knowledge demands, as can be seen in the case of the Parliament. Through economic modelling, actors can get an intuition about whether their positions withstand reality. This learning effect can increase if analyses embrace full ranges of uncertainties in their assessed scenarios.

Another implication of this analysis for economic modelers is the importance of modelling for a diverse set of actors with a diverse set of political goals, to facilitate debate on political issues. The present study and its analysis have shown that economic modelling can be used to legitimize previously articulated preferences. This is not necessarily negative, as the Commission is a political actor, and as those political decisions about the configuration of e.g. the choice of assessed targets and scenarios are taken by policymakers and policy analysts, and not by economic modellers themselves. But an acknowledgement of this role emphasizes that it could add value to policymaking processes, if other actors (such as the Parliament, or NGOs) also utilize economic modelling to challenge the knowledge claims of the Commission and kick off a competition of knowledge development on certain issues (Daviter, 2015). How could the negotiations in the Trilogues have ended, if the

Parliament would have been able to show that a 60% target would also not impact Europe's economy? How would it have changed the negotiations if there were detailed analysis of how the target impacts Eastern or Southern European Member States at national level? The adoption of the 60% target might still be unlikely, because high political issues were at stake, but opponents of such a target would have needed to argue much better why they would not agree to such a target, and thus enable entry points to mitigate their concerns in the long run.

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ANNEX 2: Interview guide

How were you involved in the modelling of the economic impacts of the Climate target 2030?

What was the insight from the modelling exercise from your perspective?

How was the 55% target decided?

What was the role of the economic analysis for the 55% goal?

How did modelling impact policy design from your perspective?

What did you learn from the analysis?

What was the process of modelling the economic impacts?

What decisions did you have to take in developing the model for the impact assessment

Why were those three models chosen?

What assumptions were made?

To what extent did modelling involve participatory methods?

What were the requirements for the model from policymaker side?

How do you think did this economic modelling influence the legitimacy of the 55% target?

How do you think does economic modelling influence the willingness of member states to commit to the 55% target?

ANNEX 3: Coding scheme

Code	Description
Modelling results	The key results that the respective model produced
Economic impact	A reference to macroeconomic impact of the Climate Target in policy documents
Model role	What was the overall role of the model in the policy process
PM model engagement	Forms of engagement of policymakers with the modelling results
Stakeholders	Other stakeholders that were involved in modelmaking
target process	Descriptions of the process of arriving at the 55% target
Participation method	The way other stakeholders were involved in modelling
Legitimacy	The influence of modelling on legitimacy
Effectiveness	The role of modelling for policy effectiveness
Policy impact	Reported impact of the model on policy design
Model development	Different steps of the modelling process